

Artificial Intelligence in Retailing: A Critical Literature Review

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Introduction

The retail industry has seen a drastic change over the last decade and is currently the most dynamic sector. The retail industry in India itself is expected to reach about US\$ 1 trillion (The Boston Consultancy Group and Retailers Group of India 10).

The way retailers used to operate is changing quickly and the reasons can be attributed to the technological implications in the sector, newer business models, big data analytics, but still by and large consumer needs drives the purchase decision (Dhruv Grewala 1).

With growing millennial population and disposable income the demand for consumer goods has increased considerably and most of the youth- the tech savvy are resorting to online shopping. The e-commerce wing of retail industry is at its peak albeit, it contributes to a smaller proportion of sales when compared to the brick and mortar stores. According to (Retail touch points) e-commerce sales are expected to grow annually by 17% and reach \$414 billion by the end of 2018.

Artificial Intelligence(AI)

According to (Jack) AI research is directed towards teaching computers to think for themselves and to improvise solutions to common problems. (Avneet 79) Describes AI as development of smart and intelligent machines and software that has the ability to learn, gather and importantly perceive the objects with the help of computation.

John McCarthy refers it as “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines.” A few of the noteworthy applications of AI seen over the past few years have been mentioned in the table 1.

Table 1 Revolution in AI

Year	Revolution in AI
1990	Neural net device reads handwritten digits
1993	Robot Polly navigates using vision
1996	Deep Blue defeats the world chess champion.
1998	Robotic toy Furby learns how to speak
2005	Robot ASIMO serves restaurant customer.
2009	Google's first self driving car.
2011	Watson computer beats Jeopardy's
2016	AlphaGo defeats GO champions using.

Source: (Makridakis 47)

Many of the large companies have started adopting AI as they are able to see and gauge the potential of AI – Traditional companies like Walmart, Berkshire Johnson and Johnson(J&J) lack behind the Digital companies like Amazon, Apple and Google in terms of market capitalization and revenue per employees (Makridakis 54). The reason behind this is because the digital companies have been investing a huge amount in acquiring start ups and internal research (CB insights). The AI software systems and industry is expected to reach US\$35,870 million by 2025 (Market Watch).One of the major fears of complete adoption of AI is huge unemployment, however a proportion of the critics have mentioned that AI may result in reduced middle range jobs, however there may be a huge demand for low and high end jobs that may end up in creating social inequality (Makridakis 58).

Retailing- Retail or retailing is defined as the sale of goods or services from a business to an individual for his/her own consumption rather than resale, the transaction itself can occur through number of different channels such as online, brick and mortar, direct sales (Shopify). With the changing lifestyles, shifting demographic characteristics many of the retailing firms are moving away from the traditional offline stores to online stores to cater to a new segment of customers who are tech savvy. With the advent of e-tailing technological advancements have exponentially increased. Retail is a rapid evolving process and business people constantly have to reinforce their mode of operation to react to new ideas/technology (Helen 44).

Artificial Intelligence in Retailing

According to (World Economic Forum 14) AI/machine learning can increase revenues through a profound understanding of consumer behaviour, while optimizing in-store pricing and assortments.

Artificial Intelligence's contribution in I) Merchandising and II) Sales Forecasting have been mentioned below.

I) AI in Retail Merchandising

Merchandising refers to the entire set of activities done to promote and sell your product once the potential customer is in the store (Business Encyclopedia). Retailers have huge amount of data and the companies who are able to analyze the data sets and generate favourable plan of actions are more likely to seal the deals (Antonio).Artificial Intelligence gives an automated conversion of business rules to a mathematical approach for product placing at any given shelf location (Cohen 1) .

The retailers are now experimenting with new techniques such as augmented reality, AI, robotics to push the retail market beyond the limits (Verma).

Few of the tools currently being used in Retailing are:

“Pepper, a humanoid robot has the ability to interact with customers and perceive human emotions. Pepper robot has led to the both rise of foot fall and sales in various stores. A store in Palo Alto, California reported a 70% rise in the footfall because of Pepper Robot. Pepper Robot is also attributed to 50% of Neo pen sales in Santa Monica.”- (Faggella)

AI Chatbots

One of the most used application of AI in retailing is the use of Anthropomorphic Information Agents (AIAs)/chatbots to provide real time product information and engage the customers (Subramanian Sivaramakrishnan 61). According to (Subramanian Sivaramakrishnan 70) most of the e-tailers have an online chat option with a human representative. Despite the fact that AIAs are commonly used AI tool, according to (Jennifer Hill 245-250) chatbots have their own limitations as they are not able to have an extensive goal-directed discussion and offers very less history of shared experience. But still people are incorporating the use of AIAs because it is capable of holding the attention of millions of users (Jennifer Hill 245-250). However, with machine learning coming into picture a whole new range of chatbots are being developed that will have the ability to answer for more complex questions and think for themselves, will be deployed at retail stores in the future (Donaldson).

Virtual Assistants

The biggest group of users of the virtual assistants are the people between the ages of 25-34, representing 26.3% of Virtual assistant users (Verma). With 83 million population in USA and 400 million in India it is quite obvious the use of virtual assistants for shopping will continue to grow in the retailing sector. Over the years many virtual assistants combined with Artificial Intelligence have been developed to optimize the shopping experience of the consumers. Few are discussed as below:

Virtual Trial Mirror

Virtual trial mirror, a duality of Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality is now being readily adopted in many of the apparel, cosmetic stores. The virtual mirror enables the customers to try on different clothes without any hassle of getting dressed and undressed multiple times (Kumar). Raymond’s store in Bangalore has recently started using virtual mirror which gives its customers a digitized experience and gives the customers a view of how the suit will look on them even before the suit is completely stitched (Venkat). Virtual Mirror has helped the retailers in improving the customer experience in the stores, helping the buyer buy right and moreover, the retailer gets valuable data about the trends, demographics and body types (Kumar).

Voice Based Shopping

Many retailers are trying to adopt the voice based shopping technology to follow the trendy virtual assistants. Walmart recently announced that it will enable voice shopping through Google Assistant (Verma).

II) AI in retail Sales Forecasting

Accurate demand forecasting is critical to boost the profitability of the retail operations and any inefficiency would either result in too-much stocks or too-little stocks, directly hampering the revenue and competitive position (Deepak and Christophher). Effective sales forecasting is necessary as it helps to anticipate production and material costs, as well as determine the sales

price (LeVee 12-16). Various researchers have developed methodologies for sales forecasting the notable methodologies have been summarised below.

Table 2

Author	Year	Methodology	Conclusion
Weigend, Rumelhart, and Huberman	1991	Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN)	It gave the relationship between input and output historic sales without complete information, and effectively solved the problem of overfitting.
Tang, de Almeida, and Fishwick	1991	Box-Jenkins method	It was able to impact the international Airline passenger Traffic and domestic and foreign car sales in the United States.
R.J.Quo	1999	Integration of Artificial Neural Network (ANN) & Fuzzy Neural Network and Artificial Neural Network (GFNN)	Considered to be a reliable method for sales forecasting as it gave same results repetitively and includes a lot of variables such as promotional, seasonal factors.

Source: (Wan-I Lee 188-196) & (R.J.)

Traditionally most of the stores used to prefer Time series data methods to forecast their sales (Wan-I Lee 189). According to (Chase 15-17) time series methods are complicated because the relationship between sales and the past time series data, does not considers the seasonal, economical factors. The probable reason behind why people used these methods was lower cost and perhaps this method has been abolished as it failed to consider all the factors (Shih 227-236). Many a time decision-makers avoided using complex models and preferred to use their intuition and heuristic (R.J. 498).

R.J. Quo put forward a model which was an integration of Genetic Fuzzy Neural Network and Artificial Neural Network. This method is considered to give reliable results as it includes a lot of variables(promotional factors) and gives the same result repetitively (R.J.)

With the advent of AI in sales forecasting, sales team are able to forecast the close deal based on the common patterns for both individual and the entire market, Spiro's AI-powered sales automation CRM is one such tool which gives an honest and a statistically based picture of where the sales team stands (Honig).

Figure 1. The architecture of the Genetic Fuzzy Neural Network (GFNN) forecasting systemSource: (R.J. 501)

Conclusion

A number of researchers have come up with their methodology for sales forecasting but very few retailers are able to use these theories effectively for implementation. There is still a huge scope for research in the field of sales forecasting, to develop a model which can be continuously reinforced with different variables such as market conditions, demographics, increasing per-capita income and location factors. In the field of Merchandising Artificial Intelligence has mostly contributed to fashion & apparel industry. Retailers are extensively trying to use Machine learning/ Artificial Intelligence for pricing by identifying price and sales patterns to facilitate smart and timely decision making. Retailers are trying to leverage Artificial Intelligence to improve product shelving, assortments with the data generated with every purchase. Owing to the prevailing market competition, globalisation retailers are adapting omni-channel retailing with Artificial Intelligence

becoming an essential part of the industry. Retailers are constantly experimenting with various technologies to increase their business intelligence quotient in order to improve the consumer experience. The main reason for adopting AI and related tools is customized shopping environment for individuals, which will lead to satisfied customers and fetch greater profits in the long run.

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